

D7.3 Recommendations on Health effects: Synthesis of Findings and Calls to Action of the Equal-Life project

Project title: Early Environmental quality and life-course mental health effects

Project Number: 874724

Project Acronym: Equal-Life

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Change
1.1	December 2024	<input type="checkbox"/> Initial version
1.2	7 th December 2024	<input type="checkbox"/> First review
1.3	4 th February 2025	<input type="checkbox"/> Second review
2.0	December 2 nd , 2025+	<input type="checkbox"/> First revision after 66 Months review

REVISION DATES		
Version	Publication date	Change
2.0	28-02-2025	
2.1	30-01-2026	Final revisions at request of external reviewers

1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 874724

D7.3- Recommendations on health effects

H2020 program	Grant agreement number 874724 (Equal-Life),
Project start date: Jan 1 st 2020	Duration: 66 months
Project Coordinator: Irene van Kamp (RIVM)	

WP (number and title)	Equal-Life WP7 - Health effect analysis
Deliverable Number	Equal-Life D7.3
Deliverable Title	Recommendations on Health Effects: Synthesis of Findings and Calls to Action of the Equal-Life project
Due date	31.3.2024
Actual date	31-01-2026
Dissemination Level	Public

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Disclaimer: This deliverable is adapted based upon request of the EC. The content is significantly different from the previous version. Therefore, not all co-authors from previous version are mentioned in this version.

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1. Summary

The EU-funded Equal-Life project aimed to investigate the complexities of the physical and social exposome and their interplay in young peoples' mental health and cognitive development in home and school settings - from birth to adolescence. This was achieved by the analysis of available data from eleven European cohorts and school studies adding up to nearly 250,000 children, enriched by exposure data of both physical and social environment and analysis of biomarkers in two cohorts (D5.5). Also, new data were collected in six tailored in-depth studies, addressing time activity patterns at different ages, school acoustics and effects on attention and learning, two sleep studies and a preschool study on cognitive effects in two countries (van Kamp et al., 2022).

This report synthesizes the key results of these health effect analyses subdivided in: Untargeted analyses using Random Forest, Targeted analysis using Structural Equation Modeling, tailored in-depth studies and proteomics and metabolomics biomarker analysis in two cohorts using a range of statistical methods. This summary of results, presented as overarching findings, sketches the bigger picture of what we can learn from this project.

The findings highlight the importance of environmental aspects on children's mental health and cognitive development, and the mediating role of sleep, stress, restoration, and self-regulation in the association between environment and mental health. These pathways play a crucial role between child's social and physical environment and effects on mental health and cognitive development, but the observed relationships were not always consistent across the different cohorts/study populations.

Core findings and calls to action are listed for the three main aspects of environments identified: 'places', 'age of exposure', and 'equity'. **Places** refer to where the children, in utero or after birth, spent time, including physical locations and the digital world. Exposures such as noise and psychological factors such as perception of safety of the place influence children's health and development.

Different exposures and factors have different effects and different levels of impact on children in different **age groups** (developmental stages). The physical and social environment during pregnancy affects child development. In early age (0-3 years old) family and household environment play a significant role. Neighbourhood characteristics and access to green space become increasingly important when children grow older and explore their environment more.

Equity has long been a key topic in public health concerning environmental injustice and structural discrimination. In Equal-Life, it is detected via identifying "exposome clusters", which are defined as groups of children sharing similar disadvantaged or advantaged physical and social exposures. Exposome clusters were found to be associated with a higher prevalence of mental health issues in children living in more deprived conditions.

The calls to action are divided in four threads: 1) intervene on mediating factors to support healthier pathways in children between exposure and outcomes; 2) promote healthy, safe, child-friendly and activity-supported "places"; 3) embed age-specific considerations everywhere all the time; and 4) improve equity consideration in intervention planning, implementation and evaluation with Equal-Life tool (framework with a logic model of the intervention process and an equity lens).

Specific actions were formulated for distinct stakeholder groups including researchers, community health professionals, educational professionals, urban planners, and policy makers and are summarized below.

Future research should consider the role of mediating factors and urban planners and health professionals should target such factors by e.g. mitigating environmental stress levels, reducing noise levels at night, promoting access to restorative green space for children.

Regarding ‘places’, contributions from researchers and policy makers are needed. The rural/urban division, and activity patterns should be investigated more. The Equal-Life tools allow for a more holistic “health in all policy approach”, and focus on green space, noise control and mitigation. A life course, developmental stage, approach is recommended with specific attention to research for children below seven, since evidence for that group is still scarce. Parental status and household environment should be a point of attention of early childhood healthcare. For children at pre-and primary school age, noise control and mitigation is important in classrooms and age-appropriate facilities and green space accessibility should be accounted for in urban planning.

Stakeholders should remain aware of equity aspects in all stages of planning, implementation and evaluation of interventions and research, and inter-disciplinary collaboration is necessary to improve actions and outcomes. Equal-Life tools like the “conceptual framework of the social exposome”, “analysis strategy to explore exposome clusters”, and “framework to consider equity in urban intervention with of logic model of the intervention process and an equity lens” can be used in future actions. Some exemplary case studies are described to translate research findings into actions and interventions.

Unravelling the complexity of factors affecting children’s mental and cognitive health requires sustained efforts and comprehensive high-quality evidence, which cannot be achieved within a single project. Findings from Equal-Life need further validation in future studies. Consequently, the appropriate use of Equal-Life findings is to generate strategic and broad policies and actions, instead of firm, highly practical, step-by-step advice.

No single intervention works in all settings; D7.3 recommendations should be tailored to specific contexts and interventions should be population-, age-, and location-specific.

Based on the overall findings, three overarching guidelines of action are proposed, including 1) “**Work together**” encouraging applying Equal-Life tools to perform multi-discipline collaborations, urban/rural perspectives, and data sharing; 2) “**Act local**” -always consider involving the community and local people in intervention designing; 3) “**Keep going**” - Equal-life research and findings should be further validated, investigated, and expanded, such as the novel findings on potential biomarkers for children mental health.

For the summaries of all Equal-Life publications we refer to the [Equal-Life Toolbox](#).

2. Background

Poor mental health is one of the fastest-growing public health challenges in Europe, with increasing awareness of its societal and economic implications. In 2018, the cost of mental ill-health in Europe was estimated to exceed 4% of GDP (OECD, 2021). Early-life mental health challenges strongly predict mental health issues in adulthood, with significant impacts on quality of life and economic participation. Alarmingly, at school age, one in ten children experiences a mental health problem requiring professional support and treatment. Experiences and exposures in early childhood are foundational to individual educational and vocational outcomes and overall social development. Developmental delays and disabilities during this period increase the risk of suboptimal health, educational attainment, and poor mental and ultimately physical health.

Given the profound impact of early-life experiences on mental health and development, a comprehensive approach is needed to understand the various environmental factors shaping these outcomes. Mental health results from a dynamic interplay of genetic, psychological, environmental (social and physical) factors. This is where the exposome concept becomes particularly relevant. The exposome encompasses all environmental exposures encountered throughout a lifetime, from external and internal sources. These include individual-level exposures (e.g., diet, physical activity, psychosocial stress, noise levels at home and school etc.) and population-level exposures (e.g., neighbourhood deprivation, youth and elderly ratios at the municipality level, average household income at the neighbourhood level, etc.). The exposome, the totality of exposures from conception onwards, provides a holistic concept within which to begin studying the impact of diverse factors across different life stages and a promising framework for understanding environmental influences on mental health and cognitive development in children.

The EU-funded Equal-Life project applied the exposome concept ([D5.5](#)) to investigate multiple exposures affecting children's development and mental health over their life course. By analysing exposure data with high spatial and temporal resolution, including physical and social dimensions, the project aimed to identify key factors influencing mental health and cognitive development. Such identification is the precursor to future policy development directed at addressing social and environmental determinants of health, increasing resilience, preventive healthcare, and early detection of developmental and behavioural issues. Effective policy development requires collaboration across sectors, including public health, urban planning, education, social sector, and environmental protection.

Preventive measures to address poor (mental) health outcomes and suboptimal cognitive development can be classified into three levels: primary, secondary and tertiary prevention also referred to as prevention, mitigation, and management (Fernandez et al., 2019). These measures need to be based on evidence and validated interventions. At this stage, the evidence of findings is in many cases, still rather incomplete and tentative and not yet sufficient for the development of evidence-based interventions to prevent, mitigate or manage mental health and cognitive issues. However, the findings of Equal-Life do allow for a set of calls to action and preventive directions for different target groups, with focus at population level rather than at the individual level, as the assumption of causality is far from reached to allow for precision prevention at the level of individual children (Vineis, 2025a, 2025b).

This deliverable outlines the first steps needed to translate Equal-Life findings into recommendations for future research, policy actions and preventive measures. A synthesis of the key findings and a comprehensive set of calls to action is presented derived from untargeted and targeted analyses of

health effects, biomarker analysis and analysis of the six in-depth studies conducted within the Equal-Life project.

After a brief summary of approach, methods and results of the four main parts of the project, and a description of tools allowing for a translation of results into actions, the findings are synthesized around three major environmental aspects: places, age of exposure and equity. Next, calls to action are formulated per aspect. Four case studies carried out in Equal-Life, evaluating interventions, provide information on equity consideration and impact of selected (urban) interventions.

3. Health effect analyses in Equal-Life

A fundamental and critical task in Equal-Life was to define the concept of exposome and key outcomes for investigation. These tasks are reported on in [D5.5](#). Definitions of external and internal exposome, are herein presented along with the specific outcomes determined. Based on these definitions and concepts, we conducted untargeted exposome analysis, and targeted pathway and mediator analysis on existing cohort and school data. Untargeted analysis refers to the comprehensive approach to simultaneously identify thousands of markers without a priori knowledge of specific targets. On the contrary, targeted analyses measure specific predefined targets of interest. The data were enriched with exposure data with high granularity (spatial resolution). Internal exposome biomarker analysis focused on potential physiological mediators and was performed in two cohorts to explore and validate the association with mental health and exposures. Six tailored in-depth studies investigated children’s activity patterns, the cognitive effects of classroom acoustics, and the effect on sleep, mental health, wellbeing and cognitive outcomes of the exposome on children in different developmental phases (5-7 years, 8-11 years and >18 years) in four different countries.

3.1 Untargeted and targeted analyses in Equal-Life

The **untargeted analysis** of the Equal-Life project explored the relation between exposure and mental health and cognitive effects, addressing the “which” question (which factors affect mental health and cognition?). “Untargeted” means that no assumptions were made before data exploration – the data speak for themselves. The untargeted analysis in Equal-Life incorporated the exposome concept developed within the project and utilized the external exposome data to the greatest extent possible. For these analyses, the Random Forest technique was used on individual cohorts and the results were combined into one overall finding by meta-analysis. All eleven cohorts/school studies available for the project contributed to this analysis. Expert teams were formed around five groups of outcomes: 1) ‘Diagnosis of mental health issues’ (Autism, ADHD, anxiety and depression), 2) ‘Cognitive development’, 3) ‘Internalizing symptoms and Externalizing behaviour’, 4) ‘Wellbeing/Happiness’, and 5) Biomarkers. Results showed which (combinations of) exposures related to the living environment of children, were the most important for children’s mental health and cognitive development. Social and physical factors (e.g., family, green/blue spaces, socioeconomic status, urban design) affect mental and cognitive health, with effects varying by age and location. Physical factors dominate at early ages, while social factors become more influential later, although inconsistencies across cohorts were observed.

Making use of the same data sets, the **targeted modelling** in the Equal-Life project focused on so-called mediating factors (see [glossary](#)) in the relation between the physical and social exposome and outcomes, addressing the “how” questions (how, through which intermediates, do factors affect the outcomes?). For these analyses, Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used, both on individual studies’ data, and on pooled data from multiple studies. For privacy (GDPR) considerations, the

pooling was carried out using a two-step approach. Thus, the pooled targeted analyses were performed solely on aggregated anonymous data, without having access to the underlying original data from individuals of the studies. In the first step, computer codes (statistical scripts) were delivered to the local data analysts. The local data analysts then ran the analyses, delivered results and correlation matrices of the variables (the aggregated data) included in the analysis to be used in final modelling. The analyses were guided by the same expert teams as described above. Again, all eleven cohorts/school studies available for the project contributed to part of the analysis, dependent on data availability.

Overall, modelling showed that relations between the exposome variables, mediators and outcomes often differed between studies, sometimes opposite to what was expected based on hypothesized effects of green space, air pollution and noise. This suggests that the cultural and geographic context is important, and that the available exposome data are in some cases proxy measurements for some unidentified causal factors, associated with our observed exposures in different ways in different contexts. One example is that many enriched variables, derived from geo-coordinates, are linked to road traffic volumes. Thus, interpretation of results is not always simple, since more roads can mean more walkability, and better access to services, but can also be linked to more noise, air pollution and less opportunities to play safely outdoors. A clear clustering of indicators related to population density was found. Exposures vary significantly between urban and rural areas and when all are linked to the degree of urbanicity, it is hard to see effects of individual factors within strata/categories of urbanicity. This finding indicates that future studies should stratify analyses by population density and interpret findings for different settings separately.

The targeted analysis produced insight in the role of mediators, although not always consistent across studies. Future research and development of interventions can be inspired by these findings but more work is needed to pinpoint the exact factors causing the association.

3.1.1 Study Population and Data

Cohorts and School Studies

The Equal-Life consortium has access to a diverse set of data sources, comprising six longitudinal cohort studies, three cross-sectional studies and two studies with a mixed design. **Table 1** and **Figure 1** outline the included cohorts/studies along with the age groups covered and geographical spread. The geographical scope primarily encompasses Western Europe, spanning seven countries. Collectively, data are available for about 250,000 children, encompassing the prenatal period until adulthood at age 21. Most of the data was gathered at a regional level, and three of the studies were conducted on a national scale.

All these studies joined the untargeted and targeted analysis, and some participated in analyses involving multiple outcomes, all dependent on data availability. Cohorts and school studies involved in the analysis for each outcome, are presented in Table 1 in more detail and in [Project data | Equal Life](#).

Figure 1 Map showing involved cohorts/studies and their geographical setting in Equal-Life project.

Table 1 Cohort/School Studies included in the Equal-Life project (van Kamp et al., 2022).

Cohort	Country	Study design	Scale	Study Period	Age range	Number of participants
ABCD	The Netherlands	longitudinal	regional	2003-2018	0-14	8266
ALPINE	Austria	cross-sectional	regional	2004-2005	0, 8-11	1251
ALSPAC	United Kingdom	longitudinal	regional	1991-2008	0-11	14541
BREATHE	Spain	longitudinal	regional	2012-2013	7-11	2878
FAIR	Sweden	longitudinal	regional	2007-2018	0-12	200000
FinnTwin12	Finland	longitudinal	national	1994-2006	11-24	5600
NORAH	Germany	cross-sectional	regional	2012	8	1243
PIAMA	The Netherlands	longitudinal	national	1996-2017	0-20	3963
RANCH	The Netherlands	cross-sectional	regional	2002	9-11	737
STARS	Sweden	cross-sectional	regional	2015-2019	13	2283
WALNUTS	Spain	cross-sectional	regional	2016-2018	11-14	700

3.2 In-depth studies in Equal-Life

Two sub studies and three tailored in-depth studies were conducted within the project. **Table 2** provides an overview of the studies, location, age range and sample size.

Figure 2 Map showing locations of the six in-depth studies.

Table 2 Overview of in-depth studies

Data collection studies	Responsible partner	Age	Number
1 Activity patterns	Netherlands	0-21	231
2. Auditory cognition in activity based acoustic settings	Germany	3-6/6-10	362 (116 pre-school) (246 primary school)
3a Preschool study in Germany	Germany	5-7	Wave 1: 113 Wave 2: 29/ 31
3b Preschool study in Belgium	Belgium	5-7	Wave 1: 42 Wave 2: 42/32
4. Sleep study on subsample of STARS cohort	Sweden	18, 19	106
5. Sleep study on subsample of Alpine cohort	Austria	8-11	156/30

The **time activity** study was performed in the Netherlands among 231 in different age-ranges ([L3-02](#)). In this field study an activity diary was kept, and GPS tracking was conducted for 7 days, supplemented with a survey into mental health, social environment, environmental perception/satisfaction). Limitations were the small sample sizes per age group with predominantly high Socio-economic status (SES). Results show that places of activities are vital determinants of child development. Their influence on mental health and cognition arises from the interaction between environmental qualities, social relationships, and subjective perception. The home (the child's own and that of others) and the neighbourhood remain important throughout childhood. Activity diversity and

autonomy increase with age, enhancing both opportunity and vulnerability. Younger children (0–7) spend most of their time in supervised, home-based activities. Older children and adolescents engage more in unsupervised neighbourhood and peer-based settings. This independence facilitates social competence and cognitive flexibility but introduces greater exposure to environmental stressors. Adolescents showed increases in sedentary indoor behaviour and reduced physical activity; factors linked to lower well-being. Time spent in the neighbourhood, time spent on social activities and time spent using social media (screen time) are related to both mental health and social indicators and possibly a source for health inequalities. Social differences in activity patterns require more research using a larger and more diverse sample to fully understand their impact.

The **classroom acoustic study (L3-15)** consisted of three main components in 362 children aged 3-11 addressing switching Attention, Listening effort and Activity based classroom noise and effects under different noise conditions and in different age groups. Results showed that in three- to ten-year-olds, intentional switching of auditory selective attention develops with age (L3-15). Listening effort increases in noisy classroom environments, in particular for younger children (6-7 yrs). A study into activity-based classroom noise revealed significant differences in noise levels between activities, with psychoacoustic loudness being the most appropriate parameter for perceptual noise assessment (L3-15). Classroom noise levels often exceed recommended limits, impeding children's speech comprehension and increasing their listening effort. Background noise disrupts word recognition, particularly in younger children. Even a small 3 dB noise increase reduces speech in noise perception accuracy by 4–7%.

Literature reviews (L3-20) revealed the very limited number of studies into the relationship the exposome (physical, social, internal exposures) and children's and adolescents' mental health. **Three in-depth studies** in the current project were designed to fill this gap and examined the interplay between the physical exposures, social exposures, internal exposures, individual lifestyle factors, mediating factors and children's and adolescents' mental health and cognition. The in-depth studies in Sweden, Germany and Belgium focused on three different age groups, i.e., 5-7 years, 8-11 years and >18 years. Two of the three studies pertain to sleep and mental health outcomes in primary school children (Austria) and adolescents (Sweden). The third study ("Preschool Study") included samples from Germany and Belgium and focused on well-being, mental health problems, and cognitive outcomes in children in the transition from kindergarten to primary school (age 5-7 years). This study was longitudinal with one measurement wave at the end of the final kindergarten year (5-6-year-olds), and the second wave at the end of the first school year (6-7-year-olds).

The **sleep study in Sweden** using a range of statistical strategies, did not obtain significant associations of exposome, mental health and sleep. The associations found were in the hypothesised direction with increasing risk of mental health among poor sleepers exposed to an unfavourable combination of physical and social aspects (lower maternal education, lower area-level socio-economic conditions and perceived social position, shorter visits to green areas, higher noise annoyance and disturbance to artificial nocturnal light, and higher night-time offline distress). Analysis also showed that being exposed to the less favourable combination of exposures increased the risk of worse sleep, both in young women and men, but with women experiencing more mental health problems and worse sleep. Specific analyses of the physiological sleep parameters, i.e., sleep efficiency, latency to REM sleep and latency to fall asleep, did not show an association with mental health. As previously shown in the literature, self-reported poor sleep and poor mental health were strongly associated (OR=3.73, 95% CI 2.15-6.49), but are hard to interpret due to bi-directional associations. While the mediating effect of sleep in the exposure-health effect relations could be shown, further research is needed to study the mediating role of sleep in more detail.

In the **Alpine sleep study** better child-reported sleep was consistently associated with better mental health across different well-being spheres (hedonic, prosocial, safety), as measured by the KINDL questionnaire. However, there was no clear association of poor sleep with the total score on the Strength and Difficulty Questionnaire (SDQ). Overall, combined exposure indices were better predictors than single exposures. Regarding physical exposome, noise levels, air pollution, proximal greenspace, and grey space were associated with sleep indicators (duration, quality etc) and mental well-being, mostly indirectly via environmental perceptions. That is, higher levels of traffic emissions and less greenspace related to more unfavourable perceptions of neighbourhood quality and safety and higher levels of perceived disturbance by noise, which in turn translated to more mental health and sleep problems. Regarding the social exposome, educational level of mother, indoor crowding (persons/room), and the quality of family relations revealed strong associations with mental health and sleep.

A **longitudinal study** into the cognitive impact of external exposome on children in the transition period from preschool to primary school was conducted in **Belgium and Germany**. In total, 155 preschoolers, 113 from the German sites and 42 from the Belgium sites, took part in the first wave of the study in the final year of preschool and kindergarten, respectively. The second wave of measurements took place one year later at the end of the first year in primary school. In wave 2, cognitive tests were conducted in 29 children at the German sites and 42 children at the Belgium sites, i.e. a total of 71 children participated in the second wave, of whom parental questionnaires on neighbourhood quality and the children's mental health and well-being was available for 63 children.

Within a mixed statistical method approach including correlation analysis, SEM, cluster analysis, regression analysis for direct and indirect (mediation) effects, the longitudinal impact of objectively measured and modelled levels of exposure to noise and air pollution as well as parentally perceived social and physical exposome (neighbourhood quality) and the children's cognitive and mental health out-comes were analysed.

Given the small samples, the correlation analyses do not show a coherent pattern of direct, bilateral relationships between physical exposure variables and cognitive test scores and the parental reported children's mental health and well-being. This is the case for the objective measures of noise (Lden, Lnight, SDI) and air pollution (PM2.5, NO2) and the perceived neighbourhood quality. Associations are observed between the children's well-being and the social component of the exposome, including the child/home language, home literacy, parental stress and parental support. Mental health as measured by the strength and difficulty questionnaire (SDQ) is associated mainly with SES, parental stress and parental support. Among the cognitive outcomes, attention (selective, shared) and language skills are related to social exposures such as SES, low maternal education, child/home language, home literacy, parental stress and support. The modelled noise and air pollution indicators are largely unrelated to the outcomes.

Multiple regression analyses for the effects of social and physical exposures in wave 1 on children's cognition in wave 2 show the importance of social exposure on the children's cognitive development. This holds for basic cognitive functions, i.e., attention control, and for complex language functions, i.e., phonological skills and reading ability. Regarding mental health and well-being, the multiple regressions confirm the findings of the correlation analyses, indicating the importance of social factors, most of all parental stress and language spoken at home.

The mediation analyses show that, parental stress mediates the impact of the perceived total neighbourhood quality (including physical and social aspects) on well-being and mental health, but it

does not explain the change in children's mental health outcomes from wave 1 to wave 2. Given that no direct effect of the perceived neighbourhood quality was found, a full mediation via parental stress is assumed to take place.

Cumulative risk analyses consistently confirmed a significant decrease in children's well-being and language outcomes **with exposure to increasing number of risk factors**. Children who scored low on the different cognitive tests were exposed to multiple environmental risks. This is an important finding especially about the issue of inequity. Environments where social and physical risks cumulate have an additional adverse impact on children and their development. Taken together, across analyses, we found a dominant role of parental stress and parental support on children's outcomes. The close association between parental and child well-being was already recognized in the 1950's by John Bowlby, the founder of attachment theory. In his talks and publications, he stated: A society that values its children should cherish their parents.

EEG-data analysis (cross sectional) showed no significant association with the physical exposome components and confirm patterns to be expected in young children.

3.3 Discovery, validation of biomarkers of mental health, and linkage to exposures

Equal-Life employed three different approaches and two cohorts to identify biomarkers in blood plasma: proteomics, metabolomics and mitochondrial DNA. For proteome and metabolome, both untargeted and targeted analyses have been performed.

Protein biomarkers

Protein biomarkers were examined in several studies using blood plasma samples from the FinnTwin12 and WALNUTs cohorts. Overall, we identified 111 proteins significantly linked to the self-reported symptoms of both internalising (like anxiety and depression) and externalising (like aggression) domains (de Sousa, Piironen, Afonin et al., 2023; Afonin et al., 2024a; Afonin et al., 2024b). Our subsequent analysis using bioinformatics tools revealed that these proteins are involved in immune responses and brain development processes. These results show that behavioural symptoms of mental unwell-being have a reflection in the biological level, although the causality and the direction of these associations remain unknown.

Additionally, we utilised a European-wide database covering Finland, the UK, and Estonia to further validate what we found. This validation confirmed that the genes responsible for 30 proteins are strongly associated with neurological, psychotic, or psychological traits (Wang et al., 2024). Thus, we found candidate protein biomarkers indicating the underlying biological processes involved in youth mental health and early psychopathology. DOIs: [10.3390/biomedicines11030818](https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines11030818); [10.1038/s41398-024-02751-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41398-024-02751-z); [10.1101/2024.12.18.24319208](https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.12.18.24319208).

Metabolite biomarkers

Similarly, metabolite biomarkers were examined in several studies using blood plasma samples from the FinnTwin12 and WALNUTs cohorts. We identified both cohort-specific and shared, functionally similar metabolites involved in energy metabolism, lipid transportation and multiple brain functions (Whipp et al., 2021; Whipp et al., 2022). The strongest evidence of metabolomic alterations linked to the mental health outcomes in adolescents and young adults was found for energy metabolism. These results mean that future research and interventions should specifically target energy metabolism and lipids.

Mitochondrial DNA biomarkers

We used plasma samples from the WALNUTs cohort to investigate the association between mitochondrial DNA and behavioural symptoms. In our analyses, no significant associations were found. This means that mitochondrial DNA does not show the potential of being used as early biomarkers of youth mental health. (Alatalo et al., 2023). Preliminary biomarker discovery took place on part of the Walnuts cohort samples. Plasma proteomic and bioinformatic data were analysed and identified significant changes in several proteins by comparing low- and high-risk groups, based on SDQ scores (de Sousa Maciel et al., 2023). Further analysis was carried out for the entire sample set of 198 Walnuts plasma using linear modelling, to identify proteomic biomarkers associated with the SDQ score. The linear association of proteins with the total SDQ and sub score were investigated (Alatalo et al., 2023).

Biomarker analyses using the FinnTwin12 cohort compared the protein-based biomarkers which were identified in the Walnuts cohort. We identified potential biomarkers in subjects with high or low risk for mental health dysfunction, as measured by MPNI. There was very little overlap with the Walnuts study results (Afonin et al., 2024).

As part of the health effect analyses, biomarkers were linked to exposures in the Walnuts and FinnTwin12 cohort. First, the associations between the mid-adolescent external exposome and plasma proteomic biomarkers of mental health was evaluated using a multivariate Bayesian model and exposome wide association study (ExWAS) for each protein for the one-to-one relationship. Subsequently the “mediation” role of omics biomarkers of mental health was explored in the relationship between the exposome and life satisfaction in adolescents and young adults (Wang et al., 2023).

Although early analysis discovered initial potential biomarkers of child mental health no common biomarkers were found between cohorts, so further replication studies are needed to validate these biomarkers.

Specific findings show that mid-adolescence exposures (lifestyle, indoor environmental quality, natural and social environments) are linked to proteomic biomarkers. (Wang et al, 2023). Plasma proteomic and metabolomic analyses in two cohorts linked biomarkers to mental health indicators (e.g., SDQ, depression, aggression). Again, these findings are inconsistent between cohorts, necessitating further replication with standardized protocols. (Wang et al., 2023). Branched chain amino acids are associated with depression in young adults from the FinnTwin12 study (Whipp et al., 2022). Ketone body 3-hydroxybutyrate is a metabolite associated with aggression. The association was replicated in an independent Dutch sample. (Whipp et al., 2021).

Greenspaces were associated with biomarkers in both cohorts, but individual biomarkers explained only weak correlations with mental health, emphasizing the role of genetic-environment interactions. Lower similarity in co-twins' exposome profiles corresponded to behavioural differences, particularly excessive drinking tied to external exposome, showing social behaviour links to internal/external exposome, as shown in the FinnTwin12 cohort (Drouard et al., 2024). The proteome is associated with obesity in adolescence and young adulthood in the FinnTwin12 cohort and was replicated in the Netherlands Twin Registry. Obesity is a risk factor for poor mental health and should be included in internal exposome analyses (Drouard et al., 2024) and finally the analyses showed that social neighbourhood exposome modestly affects late adolescent mental health. Growth factors (e.g., proportion of childless households) are linked to internalizing problems in females, showcasing that addressing social inequalities may improve the outcomes.

4. Synthesis of findings

In order to propose calls to action, we took all described health-effect findings from the Equal-Life project into account and provide a comprehensive synthesis. The project included literature reviews, untargeted and targeted analysis on existing cohorts and school studies, tailored in-depth studies in different age groups, and explored biomarkers of mental health. Important mediators (“the bigger picture”), exposures at home and school (“places”), vulnerable developmental stages (“ages”), were identified and innovative exposure data were developed. Equity assessment on one data set took place via the identification of exposome cluster reflecting socioeconomic deprivation (“equity”). Findings on biomarkers for children mental health were explored and validated. Factors identified in the exposome clusters are also seen in the in-depth studies and in (un)targeted analysis.

More detailed information about the studies and findings as well as publication information are to be found in (L3-01–20). Most documents are published or under review. For some deliverables, peer reviewed papers are not yet being prepared and these are not included in the publication overview.

The project’s findings, in short, highlight that **every aspect of a child’s environment is potentially significant for their mental health and cognitive development**. Key findings in the project are described below and can also be accessed in the Equal-Life Toolbox: [Findings | equal-life-toolbox](#).

4.1 The bigger picture: important mediators

Literature reviews in Equal-Life found that sleep, stress, restoration and self-regulation/coping mediate relationships between exposome and children’s mental health and cognitive development. Equal-Life in-depth studies and targeted analyses further examined these mediators (L3-20). For **sleep**, it was found that poor sleep patterns in childhood often remain into adolescence, which can lead to mental health issues. Exposures to traffic noise and nitrogen dioxide in ambient air and living in an urban neighbourhood with high population density with lack of green space were found to be associated with sleep problems. In contrast, having a home garden and good family relations is associated with improved sleep (L3-13). Regarding **stress**, psychological stress shows a mediating effect between exposures and mental health outcomes (L3-16). Parental stress levels mediate the impact of neighbourhood quality on mental health in preschoolers (L3-18). **Restoration** via early-life assessment to green and blue space were associated with advanced mental health and well-being. The positive impact of the greenspace–mental health association can be further enhanced by positive perceived restorative quality of living environments. Additionally, physical activity consistently associated with healthier psychological conditions (L3-19). The **self-regulation** skills in children, which promotes children’s coping with environmental stressors and harmful exposures, are influenced by parenting skills and parental self-regulation.

Based on integrative findings from literature reviews, in-depth studies, and targeted analysis in Equal-Life, we concluded that sleep, stress, self-regulation skills and restorative activities show a crucial, mediating role between a child’s environment and their mental health/cognitive development. In words, these are important mediators in the association between children’s exposures and the outcomes. A mediator is like a bridge between a factor and an outcome, helping to understand how or why an exposure affects an outcome. It describes a possible pathway of the association. Also, it implies that intervening in the mediator can potentially change the process from exposure to outcome, therefore improving mental health and cognitive functions in children. Therefore, we speak of a bigger picture finding.

4.2 Places matter

“Places” can refer to any type of physical locations or digital world where children grow up or spend time, including home, school, neighbourhood, digital world, and leisure facilities. These places have a huge impact on their well-being and development. Children’s experience of a “place” is shaped by a wide range of physical and social aspects as well as the amount of time they spend there. In addition, psychological factors, such as children’s and families’ perceptions of the place’s environment (e.g., noise, safety, etc.), can also impacts the children’s mental health.

Based on integrative findings, we conclude that cumulative and multiple exposures to factors related to activities and its settings and companions ([L3-02](#)), have a stronger influence on children’s mental well-being, than single factors. Additionally, the proportion of time a child spends in each setting, referred to as time activity patterns, also plays an important role in the relationship. Nevertheless, children’s perception determines how they interact with places, which results in changes in their exposures and mental health outcomes.

Important findings in Equal-Life related to ‘places’ can be broken down into four major aspects. **The urban/rural context** is commonly an important concern in exposure studies. In Equal-Life, exposure patterns were found to be different between populated urban areas and less-populated rural areas. This indicates that interpretations of certain exposures and their effects should be specified for the urban or rural context. For example, green-space coverage in an urban neighbourhood might refer to a small, well-designed park, while in a rural community it might be a large size of agricultural land, and their health impact varies ([L3-10](#)). On the topic of urban green areas, **urban green space accessibility** of children was found to be shaped by neighbourhood layout, green space sizes (smaller spaces are more accessible), and psychological factors such as attractiveness and motivation ([L3-01](#); [L3-17](#)).

Another important aspect is **noise**. Chronic background noise impacts motivation and cognitive persistence. Long-term exposure to chronic background noise can influence learning and emotion regulation ([L3-15](#); Seitz et al., 2024). High-sensitive measurement models for noise, a critical tool enabling relevant research and actions, was improved and tested. The upgrades include expanding geographical coverage of noise maps, adjustments for different traffic densities of major and minor roads ([L3-03](#)), estimating effects on mental health ([L3-04](#)) and outdoor-to-indoor noise propagation ([L3-11](#)). Lastly, **activity** patterns, such as social versus solitary and indoor versus outdoor activities, appear to be a stronger predictor for well-being, implying that diverse, meaningful, and socially supportive activities may mitigate the harmful effects of exposures and enhance resilience at individual level ([L3-02](#)).

4.3 Age of exposure matters

Through the Equal-Life life course approach, we were able to determine key exposures and vulnerabilities for different age groups. For example, in the prenatal stage, social factors can affect pregnant women and influence the neurodevelopment and health outcomes in their children. Before age 3 years, family and home environment is very significant. After age 3, the broader physical and social environment becomes increasingly important. When the child grows older, they engage more and further in the neighbourhood, and green space accessibility becomes more important.

Literature reviews in Equal-Life identified critical development periods when child's development and future health can be significantly affected by combined physical, internal and social exposures.

Accordingly, an age framework for a child's perspective of the exposome was developed, highlighting the following key age-ranges: prenatal, 0-3 years, 4-6 years, 7-12 years, 12-16 years, 17-21 years.

Exposure to unfavourable substances, such as tobacco, air pollutants, chemicals, metals, (not studied in Equal-Life) during **prenatal period** and **early life**, along with social factors and features of internal exposome (e.g., birth weight, duration of breastfeeding, preterm birth, biomarkers, genetic variations), was associated with later cognitive impairments ([L3-06](#)).

When children grow older, their activity patterns change from dominantly home-centred to be more independent and exploring a larger area ([L3-02](#)) in the **neighbourhood**. Children's out-home social interactions, including interactions with peers and older generations as well as greenspace access, are greatly impacted by density and layout of urban neighbourhoods ([L3-17](#)). In addition, while green space assessment has an important role for the adolescent period, barriers to access urban green space was found for them ([L3-01](#)).

At **school settings**, we found auditory selective attention improves with age. Compared to older children aged 8-10, younger children 6-7 years old have higher listening challenges in noisy classrooms and are more tired in noisy environments ([L3-15](#)).

Associations between proteomic **biomarkers** of mental health and mid-adolescence exposures related to lifestyle, indoor environmental quality, natural environment, and family environment. However, future studies are needed to further validate and to establish cause and effect ([L3-05](#)).

Cohort-specific and shared, functionally similar metabolites were identified, involved in energy metabolism, lipid transportation and multiple brain functions (Whipp et al., 2021; Whipp et al., 2022). The strongest evidence of metabolomic alterations linked to the mental health outcomes in adolescents and young adults was found for energy metabolism. These results mean that future research and interventions should specifically target energy metabolism and lipids ([L3-05](#)).

4.4 Equity matters

Equal-Life findings contribute new evidence to the links between social inequalities and child mental health issues. We developed a Social Exposome conceptual framework, which provides a holistic view on how the social environment - from the immediate individual-level up to the broadest societal context at population-level - in its totality systematically impacts upon health. View publication ([L3-14](#)).

The concept of "**exposome clusters**" refers to groups of children who share co-occurring physical and social exposures, such as children living in an economically deprived neighbourhood, with, limited access to green space, or having a mother with mental health difficulties. In Equal-Life, exposome clusters were assessed based on the Social Exposome Conceptual Framework in a child cohort in Amsterdam. Eight "exposome clusters" were identified. Living in more deprived neighbourhoods and higher prevalence of maternal mental health problems are linked to higher prevalence of mental health issues in children. In the conceptual model, we referred to these aspects as "socioeconomic circumstances and sociodemographic characteristics and "relational dynamics", respectively ([L3-09](#)). Integrative analysis of different parts of the study showed that the role of some factors in the exposome clusters were also observed in the in-depth studies and (un)targeted analysis.

A tool to prioritise social equity in research and interventions, referred to as Equity Lens, was developed. The tool (framework to consider equity in urban intervention planning, implementation

and evaluation) is composed of a logic model of the intervention process and the equity comprising questions mapped to an intervention process (planning, implementation and evaluation) and covering key aspects of environmental justice. An example of using the tool is in the practice improving the consideration of equity aspects in the Play Space Policy for the city of Utrecht in the Netherlands ([L3-07](#)) as described in chapter 5 and Annex 1.

4.5 Logic models translating research into action

The Equal-Life project also considered where and how the available project findings, as in the syntheses above, could be incorporated into future research and into the work of practitioners. Two highly related logic models were developed and applied, one generic model and one specifically focused on equity aspects of urban interventions ([L3-07](#)). A logic model is a hypothesized description of the chain of causes and effects leading to an outcome of interest. Logic models can serve as practical tools for planning, implementation, and evaluation, ensuring that all aspects of the intervention are aligned and systematically addressed. By mapping the logical sequence of interventions and expected outcomes, stakeholders can better understand the pathways by which elements of an intervention change the situation. Finally, logic models also serve as valuable tools for monitoring and evaluation. The Equal-Life case studies described in chapter 5 and Annex 1 evaluating policies, show examples of such applications.

4.5.1 Equity Lens

The framework consisting of a logic model and an equity lens developed in Equal-Life is focused on equity aspects of interventions ([L3-07](#)).

The framework was developed through extensive literature searches, inter- and transdisciplinary discussions, completed with expert knowledge. It was applied to one of the four case studies (Play Space Policy, city of Utrecht, NL) (Mobility Hub, Utrecht NL) (Cycling project, North Macedonia) (Noise Action Plans, Slovenia). The comprehensive framework (**Figure 3**) addresses all phases of urban interventions (initial situation, planning, implementation, evaluation), emphasizes environmental justice, and incorporates the Health in all Policies (HiAP) approach, making it a versatile tool for equity assessment across sectors. The framework consists of a generic logic model for interventions in the form of a visual representation as well as an equity-lens in the form of questions that can be used as prompts by practitioners to embed an equity perspective into their work.

The equity-lens of the framework (in the form of guiding questions, not show in detail here) can be applied to the specific components of the logic model and identify the important equity aspects that need to be considered during the entire process from an environmental justice perspective. The generic logic model and the equity-lens can be applied to and elaborated for specific interventions. Applying the framework to the case study revealed previously overlooked equity aspects and highlights how thorough consideration of equity aspects in urban intervention planning, implementation and evaluation will promote health equity.

Figure 3 Generic framework to consider equity in urban intervention planning, implementation and evaluation with the logic model of an intervention process and the equity lens, consisting of equity-related questions covering the three main dimensions of environmental justice.

5. Calls to action

Presented below are the specific recommendations based on the different aspects of the project's integrative findings (paragraphs 5.1-5.4). The recommendations are presented for different roles, including researchers, community health professionals, educational professionals, healthcare professionals, urban planners, and policy makers.

5.1 Actions Derived from The Bigger Picture of Equal-Life Studies

Based on overarching results on mediators (paragraph 4.1), we propose the following:

Actions for **researchers**:

- In future research evaluating the effect of exposome, the role and impact of psychological stress should be considered, and the focus we recommend is on the “feedback loop” or two-way dynamic between stress and children mental health outcomes.

Assess the relationship between self-regulation and childhood mental health by comparing studies using high-quality standardized psychometric instruments, latent profile/cluster analyses and network models.

Actions for **community health professionals**:

- In parental support programs, prioritise establishing healthy sleep patterns at an early age of children which can reduce the risk of later mental health issues and cognitive impairment, and increasing awareness of the role of good family relations in promoting healthy sleep.
- Parental support programs should also focus on developing parents' and caregivers' skills in co-regulation and support, which have positive influences on children's self-regulation skills.

Action for **policy makers and planners**:

- A supportive built environment is critical for promoting healthy sleep. Measures improving healthy sleep patterns could include: expanding Low-Emission Zones (LEZs), traffic calming measures, and creating quiet zones and green, restorative spaces in dense urban neighbourhoods.

5.2 Actions derived from Equal-Life findings on ‘places’

Based on overarching results on “Places” (Chapter 4.2), we propose the following recommendations:

Actions for **researchers**:

- Future exposome research should take into account the rural/urban divide. Population density is a classic proxy/indicator of urbanity, but insufficient in the sense that it does not address the complex underlying factors that matter. Thus, one should go beyond this simple metric and form hypotheses about underlying factors or interpreting results, depending on whether the study population is from a high or low density area.
- Activity patterns need to be further investigated, in particular the roles of social differences and structural inequities, caused by the societal context of culture, beliefs and political systems and implying for example of inequality in access to healthy environments and amenities.

Actions for **policy makers**:

- Take a holistic approach – using the Equal-Life conceptual model:
 - Policies should account for multiple factors, including mobility, accessibility and social factors such as motivation. Also, policies should be age-specific and context-sensitive, integrating urban design, public health, and education, in order to foster environments that support safe autonomy and social connection.
- Apply Equal-Life’s findings with respect to urban structure and environment
 - This approach enhances the precision in measuring and quantifying the physical aspects of urban cities, towns and neighbourhoods. This provides potential for designing effective, local-level and local-specific interventions to address children’s specific needs and vulnerabilities.
 - Green space-relevant policies need to be included in this holistic approach. Policies relevant to different aspects of green space are needed. For example, urban green spaces should offer attractive, age-appropriate facilities, increasing opportunities for social interactions, feel safe, and be easy to access on foot. Specific design recommendations include:
 - Noting the barrier effect of large green spaces; prioritizing smaller and accessible green spaces for children.
 - Considering density and relevance of facilities (e.g., schools, playgrounds) and surrounding street networks of green spaces.
 - Reducing children’s mobility restrictions due to traffic and barriers.
- Noise-relevant policies are needed:
 - Noise measurement techniques should be child-centred, focusing on the impact on children mental health and their time spent in different settings ([L3-02](#)).

5.3 Actions derived from Equal-Life findings on ‘ages’

Based on overarching results on “Ages” (Chapter 4.3), we proposed the following recommendations:

Actions for **researchers**:

- Apply the Equal-Life conceptual framework in future studies with larger study samples to assess how the exposome interacts with life course susceptibility from pre-natal to late adolescence.
- Particularly, more research is needed in investigating age groups under 7 years old, and focusing on exposure levels and social economic status.
- The mediating role of stress between different exposures and mental health and cognitive development need to be further studied, also in age groups below 7 since evidence is lacking for this group.
- The exposome research field needs a global, cultural, and rural/urban perspective on exposure, as well as the distribution and timing of exposure, and societal support.

Actions for **educational professionals**:

- Improve classroom acoustics by reducing noise levels in classrooms. The noise levels should be lower than 55 dB(A) for silent work and below 67 dB(A) for group work.
- Include psychoacoustic metrics like loudness (perceived intensity) and sharpness in noise assessments, which help to better reflect auditory perception in classrooms. Use child-sized artificial head microphones to fit children’s smaller ear canals and head sizes.

Actions for **healthcare professionals**:

- Early childhood interventions should include a focus on parental health and stress. Consider to address the causes of stress (e.g. unemployment, bad working conditions, housing of poor quality) and provide health support for parents in need.

Actions for **urban planners**:

- Noting the high importance of having age-appropriate facilities for frequentation of restorative spaces, perceptions of safety, and motivation for parents and children at all age range.
- Prioritizing greenspace provision for adolescents and should taking into account their walkable (and bikeable) “commuting” routes.

5.4 Actions derived from Equal-Life findings on ‘equity’

Actions on improving equity are important for creating a child-friendly and -beneficial environment for children’s development and health for all children. Inter-disciplinary teams aiming to improve children’s environment for improved mental health and cognitive development outcomes can adopt Equal-Life’s findings to prioritize equity at all stages of planning and implementing urban interventions and research projects, and to identify socially disadvantaged / economically deprived groups who may benefit from such efforts. Following actions are recommended based on overarching Equal-Life results on “Equity” (Chapter 4.4):

Actions for researchers

- Apply the “*Social Exposome conceptual framework*” with its interface with the physical environment as a strategic map in research to demonstrate the impact of the social environment in conjunction with the physical environment.
- Collect data on the different dimensions of the Social Exposome to capture processes of discrimination and privileged treatment, avoid to conceptualize social factors merely as individual characteristics and possible confounders.
- Use our exploratory statistical approach to identify “exposome clusters”, which can help pinpoint particularly disadvantaged social groups as a starting point for developing specific and targeted interventions to improve their living conditions.
- Apply the “*Framework to consider equity in urban intervention planning, implementation and evaluation*” to evaluate equity impacts of urban interventions.

Action for policy makers / practitioners

- Employ the “*Framework to consider equity in urban intervention planning, implementation and evaluation*” with its logic model of an intervention and an equity-lens to promote a health equity-perspective in all phases of an urban intervention – from scoping and planning to implementation and evaluation.
- Co-create interventions together with the relevant dialogue groups to ensure environmental justice.

5.5 Lessons learnt from case studies in Equal-Life

General

Improving population health while addressing health inequities is a key challenge for policy makers, particularly in urban settings. Effective interventions must consider the inequitable distribution of beneficial and harmful environmental exposures, as well as differential vulnerabilities. To ensure equity, interventions should be assessed for their impact on social inequities in health, considering the dimensions of environmental justice: distributive, procedural, and recognitional justice that collectively contribute to a just and equitable society. In Equal-Life we conducted four case studies evaluating four interventions/policies in different European countries (Play Spaces Policies (Utrecht, NL), Mobility Hub (Utrecht, NL), Cycling project (North Macedonia) and Noise Action Plans (Slovenia)). Strengths, weaknesses, and suggestions for improvement were discussed for all the cases, providing a set of advice for future interventions/policies protecting children’s and teenager’s mental health and cognitive development and against inequity (Ahrens et al., 2026).

Specific

Consider these suggestions when developing, evaluating, or modifying policies and interventions.

- Sociodemographic and socioeconomic characteristics should be considered in prioritization of population/districts, planning, and implementation.
- Follow the available national/local guidelines and standards of environmental quality.
- Improve inclusivity, and avoid having inclusivity only at a surface level:
 - Involve the children and teenagers themselves. Instead of only or mostly the parents or adults working with them.

- Involve the public. Increase the awareness of the public to be involved in public affairs, from planning to implementation and evaluation. Organize activities, surveys, focus groups, or other suitable forms of activities, to have the public's input.
- Reduce barriers:
 - Language barriers; Multi-language instructions, in-person assistance
 - Digital barriers; In-person assistance on digital skills
 - Financial barriers; Discounts, multiple options/models
- Actively adapt and upgrade the plans and implementations based on the feedback from the public.

Annex 1 provides a summary of the findings of the four case studies in factsheets. For a full paper we refer to [L3-07](#).

5.6 Glossary

Bidirectional

Bidirectional processes are dynamic interactions between factors, such as physical activity, sleep or stress, and health outcomes. Take stress, sleep, coping, self-regulation, and physical activity as an example, the first four factors can influence the willingness to engage in physical activity, while physical activity can improve the levels of the four factors.

The complexity of these bidirectional dynamics between different exposure pathways, mediators, and outcomes has been highlighted by several Equal-Life studies, including those on sleep ([L3-13](#)) and restoration ([L3-19](#)). The need of more research into these interactions are emphasized.

Exposome clusters

An exposome cluster is a group of people sharing similar environmental exposure profiles representing by multiple variables of the societal, social, built and natural environment. For example, an innovative Equal-Life study identified several exposome clusters among a child cohort in Amsterdam. A following step analysed distributions of mental health-related outcomes across those clusters. The study found that in general, the more deprived of the neighbourhoods and the higher the prevalence of maternal mental health problems, the higher the prevalence of children with mental health issues (D7.3 Chapter 4.4 Equity).

Exposome clusters identification is an innovative, discovery-based approach based on exposures of societal, social, built and natural environments. It is hypothesis-free and simultaneously examines a large range of exposures while avoiding a-priori linkage with a predefined disease.

Equity

Scientific evidence shows that physical and social environmental factors interact to produce health inequities, in the form of unequal distribution of environmental hazards and benefits, but also recognition and procedural justice. Environment is the totality of various external physical and social environmental influences, social environmental influences.

Populations with unfavourable socioeconomic and social dimensions are more exposed to environmental hazards. While health inequalities address general differences in health without normative judgement, unequal distributions which

are assumed to be unfair, unjust, and avoidable, particularly when linked to social determinants of health, are referred to as health inequities.

ExWAS

Exposome-wide association study

ExWAS is a data-driven analytical approach for large-scale exploratory studies in exposomics, inspired by the GWAS (genome-wide association study) paradigm in human genetics. It works across different study designs, including but not limited to: cross-sectional, cohort, longitudinal, and (nested) case-control studies. It is also highly interpretable as it can be driven by a variety of methods based on regression and other techniques. Fundamentally, ExWAS attempts to systematically model all the pairwise relationships between a single phenotype and multiple exposures, aiming to identify statistically significant associations while controlling for the effects of multiple comparisons.

In Equal-Life the ExWAS approach was used on the FinnTwin12 cohort (3,025 participants in young adulthood and 4,127 at age 17), to identify significant exposures from 12 domains. In ExWASes, 29 and 46 exposures were significantly associated with depressive symptoms in young adulthood and at age 17, respectively, and familial exposures were the most influential. Twin models indicated considerable genetic and environmental covariances between the exposome score and depressive symptoms with sex differences (Wang et al., 2023)

For more information on ExWAS: <https://doi.org/10.1093/exposome/osae001>

Mediator

A mediator is an intervening factor on the causal path between exposures and outcomes, meaning that that it “is caused by” the exposure and in turn “causes” the outcome (VanderWeele 2016). This means that there is a temporal order of the appearances of the exposure, mediator, and outcome, with the mediator appearing after the exposure but before the outcome. For example, noise (as an exposure) affects parental stress (as a mediator), which affects mental health in children (as an outcome).

Equal-Life research focused on the mediating role of sleep, stress, restoration, and self-regulation/coping (L3-20) in relation to child mental health outcomes.

5.7 Guiding principles of action

Based on the overarching findings and calls to action described above Equal-Life proposes three guiding principles of actions, namely:

- **“Work together”**: Multiple uses of Equal-Life’s *tools*, including: 1) Design interventions collaboratively across professional disciplines; 2) Advance insights into urban exposome with sophisticated measuring and analysis methods; and 3) Share resulting examples and data.
- **“Act local”**: Involve the relevant community, co-design neighbourhood-level interventions with local people.

- **“Keep going”**: Equal-Life has identified many research topics for further studies, including ([L3-05](#)) potential proteomic and metabolic biomarkers of depression and anxiety’. These findings on biomarkers need to be further validated and expanded, and be examined for their ethical implications ([L3-08a](#) [L3-08b](#)).

6. End conclusion

Equal-Life’s interdisciplinary team harvested the results of the different parts of the project and integrated these in key findings and calls to action which are also included in the Equal-Life tools and Guidebook (publicly accessible: www.equal-life-toolbox.eu).

Places, age of exposure and equity were identified as core aspects of child environment. Places where children grow up and how and where they spend time impact their development. Physical and social factors combined explain more about mental health than either alone and effects are often indirect. Family life, access to green and blue spaces, environmental quality, and neighbourhood design all matter, and differ by age, city, and country. Mental health problems and delays in cognitive development are more common in socially deprived areas, showing structural social inequalities.

Access to green space/playgrounds, at home and elsewhere, correlates with improved mental and cognitive outcomes. Proteomic and metabolomic profiling showed links to mental health risk markers, but no robust, cohort-shared biomarkers have been identified yet. Mid-adolescence exposures related to lifestyle, indoor environmental quality, natural environment, and family environment were associated with proteomic biomarkers of mental health. The first results are promising, but too premature to contemplate early screening of biomarkers for mental health. The evidence-base needs to be strengthened and future studies should consider ethical aspects and the risk of medicalisation of childhood.

The findings present numerous opportunities for intervention. Designing interventions based on the analyses is challenging due to the still limited evidence on early exposome and their impact on mental health and cognitive development. Furthermore, it is essential to consider both physical and social environmental exposures.

Results highlight the need for holistic, multi-domain approaches in child health policy. Interventions should integrate equity considerations to avoid exacerbating existing social gradients in mental health. The exposome concept is still unfamiliar to stakeholders and translation of findings into actionable policy remains a challenge, requiring user-friendly tools and frameworks with focus on preventive action.

The Equal-Life Toolbox and guidance documents support policymakers in scenario planning and prevention and were fully integrated in the EHEN Network Toolbox page, ensuring alignment with project objectives, results and user needs. Implementation was reinforced through training sessions, facilitated and widely adopted by diverse user groups from 31 countries. The Toolbox and Guidebook will remain publicly accessible beyond the project’s duration.

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Annex 1 Equal-Life case studies

Cycle Infrastructure

Aspect of the environment	Built environment, transport infrastructure
Topic	Cycling infrastructure
Overall goal	Improvement of bicycle infrastructure and encouragement in cycling behaviour of citizens for sustainable transport
Location	Skopje, North Macedonia
Data sources	Stakeholder interviews, review of relevant policy documents
Intervention	Provision of a bicycle-friendly infrastructure, integration of bicycle traffic into the multimodal transport system and application of intelligent transport systems for cycling, financial support for bicycle use (provision of cycling subsidies and a cycling-friendly tax system).
Stage of process	Implementation ongoing
Application of the equity-lens: Lessons learnt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sociodemographic and socioeconomic inequalities of the population were not considered during the planning and implementation of the bicycle traffic improvement plan. Considering inequalities would beneficially inform the implementation of the traffic improvement plan to develop safe conditions for cycling for everyone. - During the planning phase, the perspective of children and youth should be considered by including professionals experienced in working with children and young people. - More diverse participatory approaches including discussions and public debate on municipality level should be used. - The overall focus of the intervention implementation should be on municipalities with higher density of population and lower socioeconomic status. - Unemployed citizens and those with lower education level would benefit from subsidies schemes. - Evaluation should be conducted on a public level and should include municipalities with lower education level and higher unemployment rates.
Further information	None

Mobility Hubs

Aspect of the environment	Transport infrastructure, social infrastructure
Topic	Transport poverty
Overall goal	Improving use of shared mobility and supporting transport accessibility, reducing transport poverty
Location	Utrecht, the Netherlands
Data sources	Review of policy documents, discussions with persons in charge, focus groups with residents
Intervention	Implementation of a shared mobility hub providing shared electric bicycles, shared electric cargo bicycles, and shared cars in Kanaleneiland neighbourhood.
Stage of process	Pilot study completed
Application of the equity-lens: Lessons learnt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A preliminary survey to collect quantitative data on how to make the hub fit for purpose in helping people meet their mobility needs showed a very low response rate. To include their perspective adequately, focus group discussions prior to the implementation would be valuable. Instead, the focus groups were conducted during the implementation phase. - Overall communication strategies should be improved to gather data about the most appropriate intervention from the potential users' perspective to address their mobility needs. - Data on transport poverty at neighbourhood level would have been beneficial during the planning phase. - Usage data of the mobility hub should be linked to information on user profiles regarding sociodemographic/socioeconomic characteristics. - Data on mobility needs should be collected before and after the implementation to verify whether the hub had addressed unmet needs for the residents. - A process evaluation would have helped on reflection how public engagement could have been improved.

Further information	Tönnies J, Ahrens J, Hasselder P, van Houten P, van Eerten JJ, White, M, Weber M, & Bolte, G. Tackling transport poverty with offers for shared mobility – a qualitative analysis on mobility needs and barriers in the context of a new mobility hub in a deprived neighbourhood. <i>Cities & Health</i> . 2025:1–15. doi:10.1080/23748834.2025.2539608
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Noise Legislation

Aspect of the environment	Physical environment
Topic	Legislation of EU noise policy
Overall goal	Reduction of environmental noise exposure
Location	Slovenia with a particular focus on the city of Ljubljana
Data sources	Review of legislation documents, collection of secondary data from national statistical office, discussions with stakeholders
Intervention	Implementation of Environmental Noise Directive (END) 2002/49/EC and preparation of Noise Action Plans in Slovenia, and in Ljubljana in particular
Stage of process	Evaluation completed
Application of the equity-lens: Lessons learnt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During the planning phase, more experts to better plan the new legislation should have been included. - The END was not implemented by including population groups as suggested in its text, but rather as already outlined in the national environmental act. - Citizens were only involved at the very final stage of the document or plan, where they could submit comments. - They had no opportunity to further discuss their comments if these were not taken up by the competent authority. - The END should be implemented with less deviations on articles important for public involvement and planning of targeted measures.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Announcement of information in public should also consider more vulnerable populations with using several options for information important to reach all citizens in time. - For the evaluation phase, the Ministry of Environment and Spatial Planning and the Municipality of Ljubljana should orientate according to the Operational program. - In the Operational Plan, more strict deadlines and more targeted actions should be listed. - Target limit values from END should be respected to reduce the number of people exposed to environmental noise above 55 dBA during the whole day and 50 dBA during the night. - Slovenia should fulfil the END requirements so that the Operational program is mandatory for the most critical areas of noise exposure following from the strategic noise maps. - Socioeconomic aspects should also be considered at least including vulnerable populations for example children in kindergartens and schools.
Further information	<p>Jeram S, Frigelj N, Kralj M, Ristovska G, Boljka U, Škafar M, et al. Implementation of the Environmental Noise Directive 2002/49/EC in Slovenia seen through an equity lens. 14th ICBEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem. 2023.</p> <p>https://www.icben.org/2023/presenting193.pdf. Accessed 19 Nov 2025</p>

Play Spaces Policy

Aspect of the environment	Built environment, social infrastructure
Topic	Assessment and improvement of play spaces for children as part of the built environment
Overall Goal	Provision of adequate and safe play areas for all children
Location	Utrecht, the Netherlands
Data Sources	Review of documents, discussions with persons in charge, stakeholder interview, literature review

D7.3- Recommendations on health effects

Intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Play Space Policy aimed to update the Play Space Standard that provides the basic assessment of qualitative and quantitative criteria to assess the availability and suitability of play space in individual districts and if it is within a walkable distance of children’s homes.
Stage of process	Implementation
<p>Application of the equity-lens: Lessons learnt</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During analysis of the context, consideration of more potential drivers of inequalities in access to quality housing and neighbourhoods such as discriminatory housing policies. - During the conceptualizing phase, contacting schools in person worked better for getting feedback compared to only sending surveys online. Next step should be further involvement of residents from the neighbourhoods and schools. - For the planning phase, in addition to the socioeconomic and sociodemographic aspects already included, further characteristics (e.g. families living in relative poverty, migration experience) should be considered for the prioritization of play areas to be improved. - A greater focus on inclusivity (physical and social aspects) and different age groups (teenagers, elderly) would be beneficial. <p>In the implementation phase, multiple feedback opportunities should be provided to reach minority groups.</p> <p>Overall and during all phases, participatory approaches to include different target groups (children, teenagers) should be expanded and more diverse.</p> <p>The evaluation should comprise direct effects (e.g. accessibility and use of play spaces by all children) as well as indirect effects (e.g. development of the community, environmental impact, property values)</p>
Further information	<p>Ahrens J, White M, Jeram S, Ristovska G, Koning J, Gudi-Mindermann H, Tönnies J, Czwikla G, Weber M, Bolte G. A new framework to consider equity in urban intervention planning, implementation and evaluation: development and application in a case study on an urban play spaces policy. 2026. BMC Public Health.</p>